

Original Article

Publication History:

Received 25/7/2020

Accepted 18/8/2020

Published 4/9/2020

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4021005

Corresponding Author:

Muhammad Sadam Hussain
T.M.A Rural Dispensary
Muzafargarh
drsadamhussain388@gmail.com

Cite this article as:

Hussain MS, Fareed G, Kareem Z. Prevalence of roadside accidents presenting at rural dispensaries. Int. J. Med. Dent. Allied Health Sci. 2020;2(9). 330-34

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**PREVALENCE OF ROADSIDE
ACCIDENTS PRESENTING AT RURAL
DISPENSARIES**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. MUHAMMAD SADAM HUSSAIN, T.M.A RURAL DISPENSARY MUZAFFARGARH
2. DR. GOHAR FAREED, GOVERNMENT EYE, AND GENERAL HOSPITAL SAWAMINAGAR
3. DR. ZUNAIR KAREEM, DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL DGKHAN

ABSTRACT:

A traffic collision, also called a motor vehicle collision, car accident, or car crash, occurs when a vehicle collides with another vehicle, pedestrian, animal, road debris, or other stationary obstruction, such as a tree, pole or building. This survey study was conducted at different rural dispensaries. The traffic accidents reported at rural dispensaries were received. In a period of four months, we received 45 accident cases. Out of 45 cases, 31 were motorbike accidents, 6 were fall from the height or roof, 5 were accidents of carts and 3 were collisions with tractors. There were 35 males and 22 females who were suffered in these accidents. Out of 45, 31 accidents were of minor injuries, five needed investigations and nine accidents were of severe nature.

Keywords: Roadside accidents, Motorbike accidents

INTRODUCTION:

A traffic collision, also called a motor vehicle collision, car accident, or car crash, occurs when a vehicle collides with another vehicle, pedestrian, animal, road debris, or other stationary obstruction, such as a tree, pole or building. Traffic collisions often result in injury, disability, death, and property damage as well as financial costs to both society and the individuals involved. A number of factors contribute to the risk of collisions, including vehicle design, speed of operation, road design, road environment, driving skills, impairment due to alcohol or drugs, and behavior, notably distracted driving, speeding and street racing. In 2013, 54 million people worldwide sustained injuries from traffic collisions. This resulted in 1.4 million deaths in 2013, up from 1.1 million deaths in 1990. About 68,000 of these occurred in children less than five years old. Almost all high-income countries have decreasing death

rates, while the majority of low-income countries have increasing death rates due to traffic collisions. Middle-income countries have the highest rate with 20 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants, accounting for 80% of all road fatalities with 52% of all vehicles. While the death rate in Africa is the highest (24.1 per 100,000 inhabitants), the lowest rate is to be found in Europe (10.3 per 100,000 inhabitants). Traffic collisions can be classified by general types. Types of collision include head-on, road departure, rear-end, side collisions, and rollovers.

Many different terms are commonly used to describe vehicle collisions. The World Health Organization uses the term road traffic injury, while the U.S. Census Bureau uses the term motor vehicle accidents (MVA), and Transport Canada uses the term "motor vehicle traffic collision" (MVTC). Other common terms include auto accident, car accident, car crash, car smash, car wreck, motor vehicle collision (MVC),

personal injury collision (PIC), road accident, road traffic accident (RTA), road traffic collision (RTC), and road traffic incident (RTI) as well as more unofficial terms including smash-up, pile-up, and fender bender. Some organizations have begun to avoid the term "accident", instead preferring terms such as "collision", "crash" or "incident". This is because the term "accident" implies that there is no-one to blame, whereas most traffic collisions are the result of driving under the influence, excessive speed, distractions such as mobile phones or other risky behavior. Historically, in the United States, the use of terms other than "accidents" had been criticized for holding back safety improvements, based on the idea that a culture of blame may discourage the involved parties from fully disclosing the facts, and thus frustrate attempts to address the real root causes (1-3).

MATERIAL OF METHODS:

This survey study was conducted at different rural dispensaries. The

traffic accidents reported at rural dispensaries were received. All the findings were noted on a predefined proforma. The stable accidents were managed at the rural dispensaries but the complicated or unstable were referred to special trauma centers immediately. All the data was analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. Relevant statistical analysis was performed. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

In a period of four months, we received 45 accident cases. Out of 45 cases, 31 were motorbike accidents, 6 were fall from the height or roof, 5 were accidents of carts and 3 were collisions with tractors. There were 35 males and 22 females who were suffered in these accidents. Out of 45, 31 accidents were of minor injuries and were easily managed at dispensary level. Five needed

investigations like X-ray and were referred to nearest center for investigation purposes. Nine accidents were of severe nature and were immediately referred to specialized trauma centers after basic treatment.

DISCUSSION:

In 2004, 50 million more were injured in motor vehicle collisions. In 2013, between 1.25 million and 1.4 million people were killed in traffic collisions, up from 1.1 million deaths in 1990. That number represents about 2.5% of all deaths. Approximately 50 million additional people were injured in traffic collisions, a number unchanged from 2004. Individual roads also have widely differing performance in the event of an impact. In Europe, there are now EuroRAP tests that indicate how "self-explaining" and forgiving a road and its roadside would be in the event of a major incident.

In the UK, research has shown that investment in a safe road

infrastructure program could yield a 1/3 reduction in road deaths, saving as much as £6 billion per year. A consortium of 13 major road safety stakeholders have formed the Campaign for Safe Road Design, which is calling on the UK Government to make safe road design a national transport priority. India recorded 105,000 traffic deaths in a year, followed by China with over 96,000 deaths. This makes motor vehicle collisions the leading cause of injury and death among children worldwide 10–19 years old (260,000 children die a year, 10 million are injured) and the sixth leading preventable cause of death in the United States (45,800 people died and 2.4 million were injured in 2005). In the state of Texas alone, there were a total of 415,892 traffic collisions, including 3,005 fatal crashes in 2012. In Canada, they are the cause of 48% of severe injuries (4-6).

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